

METAPHORICAL AND FIGURATIVE ANALYSIS OF COLOR HYPONYMS IN THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES.

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ABSTRACT

This thesis examines the metaphoric and figurative use of hyponyms and hypernyms in the English and Uzbek languages, illustrating how these semantic relationships enrich both languages by expressing complex concepts, emotions, and cultural values. Through a comparative analysis of color metaphors the study highlights the symbolic meanings attributed to these colors and their cultural interpretations.

Keywords: Metaphoric, figurative, connotation, hyponyms, hypernyms.

Introduction. The metaphoric and figurative use of hyponyms and hypernyms in English and Uzbek enriches both languages, allowing speakers to express complex concepts, emotions, and cultural norms through linguistic units. English frequently employs hyponyms and hypernyms in metaphorical and figurative contexts to convey abstract concepts or to emphasize certain qualities. Uzbek also utilizes hyponyms and hypernyms metaphorically, often reflecting cultural values, social practices, or natural elements significant to the region. We analyze color metaphors to show hyponymic relationships in both languages. Color, as a universal phenomena, is a significant aspect of the human experience and is used in our daily lives. People always use color words to express their understandings and perceptions. In both English and Uzbek, color terms function as hyponyms under broader conceptual categories and frequently carry metaphorical meanings. These metaphors reflect the way each language conceptualizes the world, using colors to symbolize abstract ideas, character traits, and social norms. Here are several examples:

1. Black / qora. It often represents something negative or evil (“black-hearted” - prone to commit or wish evil) [1] in both languages, but can also signify elegance or sophistication (“black tie event”).

For example:

- “The black-hearted villain of melodrama isn't a patch on me when I'm stirred [2].
- “Ey qora yurakli boyqush, bundan senga qolg'an vayronani qutlamoq uchun keldim”. [3]

In the sentences mentioned, the color hyponyms aren't used literally but metaphorically. The term “black-hearted” is utilized metaphorically in both languages to convey a negative connotation.

2. White / oq. White symbolizes purity or innocence (“white as snow”), and can also denote surrender, as in “waving the white flag”. Like in English, it symbolizes purity and peace in Uzbek as well. In some contexts, it can also represent emptiness or blankness (“oq qog'oz” - blank paper).

For example: “White lie” - a minor, polite, or harmless lie [4]. “Oq ko'ngil” - a person with pure heart.

- “She told a (little) white lie as her excuse for missing the party”.
- “Oq ko'ngil insonlar ko'paysin”.

3. Red / qizil. Red can represent anger (“seeing red”), passion, or intense emotions. It also indicates danger or the need for caution, as in “red flag”. Red in Uzbek can symbolize beauty and health, as in “yuziga qizil yugurdi”, which is often a sign of good health or attractiveness. It also can represent danger or prohibition.

- “This should have been a red flag to everyone, regardless of what they thought of Fox News” [5].
- “Bemorning yuziga qizil yugurdi”.

4. Blue / ko'k. In English, the color blue carries dual figurative meanings. On one side, it symbolizes truth and justice, often seen positively as it represents constancy and reliability, illustrated in phrases like “true blue” for honesty, “blue ribbon” for the highest quality, and “blue blood” for nobility. Conversely, blue also denotes sadness and melancholy, encapsulated in the expression “feeling blue”, which describes a state of sadness or depression.

In Uzbek, the word “ko'k” is used for both the colors blue and green, indicating a different categorization of color compared to English. It is used for describing greens used in dishes (“ko'k somsa” and “ko'k chuchvara”) and can metaphorically denote the sky, as in “boshim ko'kka yetdi”. Additionally, in informal language, “ko'k” can refer to

money, specifically dollars, illustrated by the phrase “ko‘kidan bormi?” (do you have any dollars?).

The metaphoric and figurative use of hyponyms and hypernyms in English and Uzbek reveals both the shared and distinct ways these languages organize and express meaning. Color metaphors provide a compelling lens through which to observe cultural values and linguistic creativity. While both languages employ similar metaphors, their interpretations are often shaped by unique cultural contexts and historical experiences. English’s extensive vocabulary often reflects a global perspective, while Uzbek’s metaphorical expressions are closely tied to regional traditions and natural environments. These differences underscore the importance of cultural context in language learning and translation.

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